

Association Of Helicobacter Pylori With Perforated Peptic Ulcer In Pakistani Population An Institution Based Study

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Abstract

Background: Most patients with chronic peptic ulcer disease have *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) infection. In the past, immediate acid-reduction surgery has been strongly advocated for perforated peptic ulcers because of the high incidence of ulcer relapse after simple closure. Simple over sewing procedures either by an open or laparoscopic approach together with *H. pylori* eradication appears to supersede definitive ulcer surgery.

Objective: To determine the frequency of *H pylori* in patients with perforated duodenal ulcer.

Methods: In 30 consecutive patients suffering from acute peptic ulcer perforation the preoperative presence of *H. pylori* was tested.

Results: The overall frequency of *h pylori* in patients with perforated ulcer found in this study is 83%. Our study included 30 patients with diagnosed perforated duodenal ulcer at laparotomy, of which 23 (76.7%) were males and 7 (23.3%) were females. The age ranged from 15 to 84 years. The mean age was 32.9 ± 15.46 years. The site of the duodenal ulcer perforation was the lesser curvature in 3 (10%), first part of duodenum in 25 (83.3%), pre-pyloric in 2 (6.7%) and gastroesophageal junction in none of the patients. 18 (60%) patients had past history of gastrointestinal symptoms suggestive of peptic ulcer. 9 (30%) patients had past history of chronic NSAID use. 17 (56.7%) patients had history of smoking. 5 (16.7%) patients had a family past history of peptic ulcer. The mean age of the patients with a positive serology was 31.68 ± 16.07 years whereas the mean age of the patients without a positive serology was 39 ± 11.25 years; this difference was not statistically significant; $p=0.343$ which could be due to small number of patients in one of the comparative groups (25 vs 5). Out of the 25 patients with a positive serology; 19 were males and 6 were females; this difference was not statistically significant; $p=0.847$.

Conclusion: We have found a high prevalence of *H. pylori* infection in patients with perforated duodenal ulcers. An immediate and appropriate *H. pylori* eradication therapy for perforated peptic ulcers can help in reducing the relapse rate after simple closure.

Introduction

Erosive injury of the gastro duodenal mucosa leading to peptic ulcer, occurs secondary to destruction of the protective layers of the gastric mucosa by a variety of etiologies. The most important factor is *Helicobacter pylori*, a gram negative microaerophilic bacterium mostly represents a chronic infection found worldwide in the patients of perforated peptic ulcer, and other causes include non steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, immunosuppressive medications, smoking, alcohol abuse and psychological stress.

Of the several of its complications which include chronic gastritis, atrophic gastritis, MALT lymphoma, the commonest complication we come across in our emergency department is perforation. The peptic ulcer disease itself is related to different locations of the breached mucosal continuity. Further being classified into four types with respect to its location, the type one is on the lesser curvature, type two more confined to the first part of the duodenum, type three is a pre pyloric variety and the type four is present at the gastroesophageal junction³. Local injury starts with areas of erosion, the healing is complete when the inciting agent has been eradicated, and the mucosa regains its integrity, but if the inciting agent is persistent, this leads to ulcer formation in the above specified area leading to stricture formation, gastric outlet obstruction or perforation leading to peritonitis. The clinical picture of a case of perforated peptic ulcer consists of severe epigastric pain of sudden onset, tenderness, rigidity, vomiting and bleeding with or without shock.

After the resuscitation, and investigations revealing free gas under diaphragm in erect x-ray films, the patient is prepared for emergency laparotomy.

Once the diagnosis is confirmed, omental patch (Graham patch) either open or laparoscopically, followed by H. Pylori eradication therapy is suggested.

In the East, infection with H. Pylori occurs at a younger age while in the West; peak incidence is more in the adult age groups. Reported incidence varies from 90% of cases of duodenal ulcer (DU) and over 70% of gastric ulcers. There is an evident association between H.pylori infection and acute perforated peptic ulcers, regardless of chronic NSAID use.

There are a number of investigations to detect H. pylori in such patients, these can be either invasive or endoscopy based tests, i.e. rapid urease test, histology, smear cytology and culture or non-invasive tests, i.e. C¹⁴ or C¹³ urea breath test and serology.

The most effective mode of eradication therapy of Helicobacter pylori comprises of the triple or quadruples regimen.¹⁰ this drug therapy is started after there is confirmed evidence of infection with H. pylori.

Internationally there is growing awareness about the significant implication of the association with .H .Pylori leading to complications. In our local scenario we need evidence of the organism being the basis of the above mentioned complications of this disease. This study determined the association of H. Pylori in patients presenting with perforated peptic ulcer in our population.

Hence this would help in rationalizing eradication therapy of h pylori postoperatively among these patients. This in turn would help in eradication and recurrence of h pylori among these patients.

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MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study design:

Descriptive cross-sectional study.

Setting:

Study was carried out at the Department of General Surgery, Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences (PIMS), Islamabad

Duration:

Six months after the acceptance of the synopsis.

Sample size:

A total of 30 patients with diagnosed perforated peptic ulcer were included in the study.

Sampling technique:

Consecutive series

Patient selection

Inclusion criteria: Patients undergoing laparotomy for perforated peptic ulcer and were confirmed to have the duodenal or gastric perforation at laparotomy.

b) **Exclusion criteria:**

Patients who were on, or had already received eradication therapy before laparotomy.

Data collection procedure

Patients presenting with acute abdomen in the emergency department were clinically assessed and subjected to relevant radiology to confirm the diagnosis of perforation. During this work up, they were put on nasogastric aspiration, parental fluids and antibiotics and were investigated for fitness for general anesthesia and surgery. Consent for surgery and inclusion in the study, was taken and the blood sample was sent for H.pylori serology. Following preoperative preparation, laparotomy was performed under general anesthesia and perforated peptic ulcer was confirmed per-operatively. Biopsy was taken for culture and sensitivity for H. pylori with Yeoman forceps.

Date Analysis

Following variables were recorded for analysis:

Age, gender, duration of acute abdominal symptoms, chronic NSAID use, family history of peptic ulcer, smoking history, previous history of surgery, history of intake of drugs active against H Pylori, site of perforation, histology report, serology for H Pylori.

Data was recorded and analyzed by using Microsoft Excel and SPSS version 15. Quantitative variables were described as mean, range and standard deviation. Statistical analysis was done by student T-test and Chi square test.

RESULTS

1.1.1 Demographic characteristics

Our study included 30 patients with diagnosed perforated duodenal ulcer at laparotomy. 23 (76.7%) were males and 7 (23.3%) were females. The age ranged from 15 to 84 years. The mean age was 32.9 ± 15.46 years (Table 2). The median and mode was 27 and 24 years respectively (Figure 6 & Figure 7).

1.1.2 Clinical presentation

The site of the duodenal ulcer perforation was the lesser curvature in 3 (10%), first part of duodenum in 25 (83.3%), pre-pyloric in 2 (6.7%) and gastroesophageal junction in none of the patients. 11 (36.7%) patients presented within 0-10 hours, 13 (43.3%) patients presented within 11-24 hours, 5 (16.7%) patients presented within 25-60 hours and 1 (3.3%) patient presented after 61 hours. (Figure 8 & Figure 9)

1.1.3 Risk factors for peptic ulcer disease

18 (60%) patients had past history of gastrointestinal symptoms suggestive of peptic ulcer. 9 (30%) patients had past history of chronic NSAID use. 17 (56.7%) patients had history of smoking. 5 (16.7%) patients had a family past history of peptic ulcer. (Figure 11)

1.1.4 H. pylori serology

H pylori serology was positive in 25 (83.3%) patients. The mean age of the patients with a positive serology was 31.68 ± 16.07 years whereas the mean age of the patients without a positive serology was 39.0 ± 11.25 years; this difference was not statistically significant as confirmed by student's t-test; $p=0.343$. Out of the 25 patients with a positive serology; 19 were males and 6 were females; this difference was not statistically significant; $p=0.847$. (Table 3 & Table 4) and (Figure 10)

1.1.5 Histopathology

All 30 (100%) patients had features of chronic duodenitis as outlined above. All 25 (83.3%) patients with positive serology also had H. pylori on the histopathology.

Gastric metaplasia was seen in 4 (13.3%) patients. One patient had changes consistent with signet ring adenocarcinoma. (Table 5)

Figure 6– Age distribution of study group

N	Valid	30
	Missing	0
Mean		33
Median		27
Mode		24
Std. Deviation		15
Minimum		15
Maximum		84

Table 2 - Descriptive Statistics for age

Figure 7- Gender distribution

Figure 8– Site of duodenal ulcer perforation

Figure 9– Time of presentation

Figure 10– H.pylori serology results

	H pylori serology	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	P value
AGE	Positive	25	31	16	3	0.343
	Negative	5	39	11	5	

Table 3– H.pylori and age distribution

		H pylori serology		Total	P value
		Positive	Negative		
Gender	Male	19	4	23	0.847
	Female	6	1	7	
Total		25	5	30	

Table 4- H.pylori serology according to gender

Figure 11– Risk factors for peptic ulcer disease

	No of patients	%age
H pylori	25	83.3%
Gastric metaplasia	4	13.3%
Signet ring adenocarcinoma	1	3.4%

Table 5: Histopathology findings in the study (n=30)

DISCUSSION

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) infection plays a crucial role in the pathogenesis of peptic ulcer disease. More than 95% of patients suffering from duodenal ulcers and about 70-80% of patients with gastric ulcers are *H. pylori* positive.¹⁵ There are several reports in the literature regarding prevalence of *H. pylori* infection in perforated peptic ulcers.^{16, 17}

The current study aimed to prospectively evaluate the prevalence of *H. pylori* infection in patients with acute perforated duodenal ulcers. The study was conducted at Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences Islamabad in a period of six month after approval of synopsis in 2011. In 30 consecutive patients suffering from acute peptic ulcer perforation the preoperative presence of *H. pylori* was tested.

Our study included 30 patients with diagnosed perforated duodenal ulcer, of which 23 (76.7%) were males and 7 (23.3%) were females. A previous study from Peshawar on frequency of *h pylori* infection in patients with perforated peptic ulcer revealed that 45 (90.0%) of their patients were male while 5 (10.0%) were females (263 old). In another study from same region 77 (90.5%) patients were male and 8 (9.4%) were females who presented for treatment of *h pylori* infection¹⁵.

In this study the age of patients ranged from 15 to 84 years. The mean age was 32.9 ± 15.5 years. Ullah A et al found out a similar age range of their study patients where they found out 30 to 75 years with an average age of 39.9 years¹⁵. One study of 100 confirmed patients of *h pylori* associated with perforated duodenal ulcer revealed mean age of 47.0 ± 13.4 years ranging from 18 to 72 years¹⁶. All these findings of age of presentation are comparable with the results of current study.

The site of the duodenal ulcer perforation was first part of duodenum in majority of the cases (83.3%) in this study while (60%) patients had past history of gastrointestinal symptoms suggestive of peptic ulcer. A cross sectional study on factors associated with perforated peptic ulcer disease in adults reported abdominal pain in 63% of their cases.

Past history of chronic NSAID use was present in (30%) of patients and another (56.7%) patients had history of smoking in the current study. Comparatively, Sodashi KJ et al reported from Zambia that 40% of their patients had history of use of NSAIDs and 34% were regular cigarette smokers¹⁷. Another study from Japan showed NSAIDs to be risk factor for perforation in 24% cases¹⁸. Similarly, they reported that alcohol and smoking have shown to predispose to peptic ulcer perforation, as seen in 34% of their study population¹⁹. It has been witnessed historically as well as by our study that NSAIDs have clearly shown to predispose to peptic ulcer disease.

Similarly, in the current study *H. pylori* serology was positive in (83.3%) patients while histopathology results also confirmed *H. pylori* in (83.3%) study patients.

Data regarding *H. pylori* infection in perforated peptic ulcers are conflicting. Indeed, *H. pylori* infection rates range from 0 to 92 per cent^{19,20,21} Some reports show that eradication of *H. pylori* can prevent recurrent ulcer disease complications such as bleeding.²⁵ This has been demonstrated recently by Ng et al²⁶ in perforated peptic ulcers. The discrepancy between infection rates found in the literature may be attributed in part to the different populations studied. Sebastian et al²⁷ reported an infection rate of 83% in a small group of young male smokers from India with acute perforated peptic ulcers; this result is comparable to our findings. Another small study from India²⁸ with 15 perforated duodenal ulcer patients showed on the contrary that all patients were negative for *H. pylori*.

Furthermore, Sharma et al. found *H. pylori* prevalence of 61% among 44 patients from Chattisgarh region, India.²⁹ Reinbach et al.³⁰ claimed that perforated ulcers might have a different pathogenesis because in their study only 47% of the perforated duodenal ulcer patients were positive for *H. pylori*. Forty four per cent of their patients were on NSAIDs, and their study showed no difference between NSAID users and non-users in relation to *H. pylori* infection.

Another study described similar results where Matsukura et al.³¹ showed that there were no significant differences between perforated and non-surgical peptic ulcer groups for *H. pylori* serum and gene markers. Ng et al²⁶ on the other hand found a 70 % infection rate (n = 73) in perforated duodenal or prepyloric ulcer patients; their figures are similar to ours. This is barely higher than the prevalence of *H. pylori* infection in the local population, and obviously lower than would be expected among patients with duodenal ulcers. In patients not on NSAIDs they found an 80% infection rate. We, on the contrary found no difference in the *H. pylori* infection rate between the two groups of NSAID users and non-users. It would be beyond the scope of this paper to discuss the different *H. pylori* eradication regimens and their success rate. Our eradication rate of 96% is excellent.³²

Most of our patients had a significant part of their eradication therapy on an inpatient basis due to the long hospital stay required for the procedure. Therefore, we consider patient compliance as an important factor for a successful treatment. This is confirmed by previous findings.³³ While elective ulcer surgery declines significantly, the percentage of emergency operations for complicated ulcers has recently increased from 60 to 90%. Simple closure of perforation gained popularity in the presence of potent acid suppressing and *H. pylori* eradication agents.³³ Despite a high recurrence rate of up to 40% after simple suture of a perforated ulcer, definitive acid-reduction ulcer surgery is on the decrease. The high age of the patient population with its comorbidity, and the availability of efficient *H. pylori* eradication regimens may account for this move away from extensive surgery.³⁵

There are several authors who showed in randomized clinical trials that eradication of *H. pylori* prevents ulcer recurrence in patients with *H. pylori*-associated perforated duodenal ulcers. In one trial of the 99 *H. pylori* positive patients, 51 were assigned to an anti-*H. pylori* therapy and 48 to omeprazole alone. After one year, ulcer relapse was significantly lower in patients treated with an anti- *H. pylori* therapy (4.8 vs. 38.1%). Likewise, Chu et al.²⁶ concluded that recurrent ulcer disease in patients with a history of perforated duodenal ulcer is related to *H. pylori* infection. None of our patients had to undergo repeated surgery for recurrent peptic ulcer disease after simple closure of perforated ulcer and successful *H. pylori* eradication.

Peptic ulcers were believed to be caused by stress, dietary factors, and gastric acid, but the link between *H. pylori* and peptic ulcers was identified in 1983. To see the frequency of *Helicobacter pylori* infection in patients with perforated duodenal ulcer and advise eradication therapy in these patients. This cross sectional study was conducted in Surgical Unit Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar,³⁷ during January 2007–June 2008. A total of 50 cases were included in the study. Postoperatively, all patients were started on PPI treatment and serum testing for *H. pylori* was done, 34 (68%) turned out positive for *H. pylori* serologically. There is still a high frequency of *H. pylori* infection in patients with perforated duodenal ulcer. But comparing these results with the various data available, there is a significant decline in *H. pylori* positive perforated duodenal ulcer patients.

In one study from Lahore³⁴ the prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* in cases of duodenal ulcer perforation and the correlation with commonly accepted predisposing factors was ascertained. A high prevalence rate of 76.67% of *H. pylori* was observed with a M/F ratio of 6.7:1. Infection rates were maximum in the elderly and those belonging to poor social class. The results coincide with other international data and prove the causative role of *H. pylori* in perforated duodenal ulcer and the therapeutic significance of *H. pylori* eradication therapy.

In another local study from Peshawar³⁵, 94 consecutive patients suffering from acute peptic ulcer perforation were studied in a prospective clinical trial. Among these 94 patients 85.1% (80=n) were positive for *H. pylori*, which is well above the usual prevalence of 45% in normal population.

In a study 85 patients were admitted with acute perforated peptic ulcer to surgical "C" unit Lady Reading Hospital, Peshawar¹⁵. They were operated and post operatively blood sample was taken for identification of antibodies against *H. pylori* by ELISA method. All patients irrespective of gender and age who were operated for perforated peptic ulcer were included in the study. Patient who gave history of intake of H2 receptor

antagonist and Proton Pump Inhibitors up to six weeks prior to their presentation were excluded. Out of their 85 patients studied (55.3%) were positive for H-pylori. In another study from Lady Reading Hospital Peshawar¹⁵, 100 patients with confirmed diagnosis of perforated duodenal ulcer were included in a study. H pylori was found in (80%) patients on histopathology and (65%) patients on rapid urease test.

The results of our study are comparable to other national and international data on h pylori and perforated duodenal ulcers. However, one of the limitations of our study was the relatively small sample size. More studies on a larger scale in future can help in demonstrating this association with greater power.

CONCLUSION:

We have found a high prevalence (83.0%) of H. pylori infection in patients with perforated duodenal ulcers. All the cases of h pylori were confirmed by both serology and histopathology tests. Male patients were in dominant in the current study. Our data can not be generalized at national level. Thought the frequency of h pylori in peptic ulcer disease patients is comparable with previous evidence. It is mandatory to conduct large scale studies on this topic to validate these conclusions.

It can be suggested that an immediate and appropriate H. pylori eradication therapy for perforated peptic ulcers can help in reducing the relapse rate after simple closure. H. pylori infection status should be assessed at the initial endoscopy or operation, regardless of concomitant NSAID intake.

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